

Correction to: Dibenzoanthradiquinone Building Blocks for the Synthesis of Nitrogenated Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons

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GENERAL METHODS AND MATERIALS:

Reagents for synthesis were, if not otherwise specified, purchased from Merck, Fluka, Acros or Fluorochem. Commercial chemicals and solvents were used as received. THF, DMF and toluene were dried using an Innovative Pure Solve solvent purification system.

Analytical thin layer chromatography (TLC) was done using aluminum sheets (20x20cm) pre-coated with silica gel RP-18W 60 F254 from Merck. Column chromatography was carried out using Silica gel 60 (40-60 μm) from Scharlab.

If heating was required for reactions magnetic hot plate stirrer with a temperature sensor and an aluminum dry heating block attached was employed.

NMR spectra in solution were recorded on a Bruker Avance III 400 MHz spectrometer at 298 K using partially deuterated solvents as internal standards. Coupling constants (J) are denoted in Hz and chemical shifts (δ) in ppm. Multiplicities are denoted as follows: s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, m = multiplet, br = broad. COSY and/or HSQC experiments were acquired to confirm precise molecular conformation and to assist in deconvoluting complex multiplet signals.

Mass Spectrometry experiments were recorded in a Ultraflex III (Bruker Daltonics) MALDI-ToF (frequency-tripled (355 nm) Nd:YAG laser) or UPLC-MS using ESI coupled to an TOF detector by Dr. Javier Calvo (CIC Biomague).

ATR-FTIR spectra were recorded on a Bruker ALPHA ATR-IR spectrometer.

X-ray data collections were performed in an Agilent Supernova diffractometer equipped with an Atlas CCD area detector, and a $\text{CuK}\alpha$ micro-focus source with multilayer optics ($\lambda = 1.54184\text{\AA}$, 250 μm FWHM beam size) by Dr. Leire Sanfelices (SGiker, University of the Basque Country). The quality of the crystals was checked under a polarizing microscope, and a suitable crystal or fragment was mounted on a Mitegen MicromountTM using Paratone-N inert oil and transferred to the diffractometer. The samples were kept at 150(10)K with a Oxford Cryosystems Cryostream 700 cooler.

Absorption spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 950 spectrometer.

Fluorescence spectra were recorded on a LS55 Perkin-Elmer Fluorescence spectrometer.

Electrochemical measurements were carried out on a Princeton Applied Research Parstat 2273 in a 3-electrode single compartment cell with glassy carbon disc working electrode, a platinum wire counter electrode and a silver wire pseudoreference electrode. All the potential values are reported versus the redox potential of the ferrocene/ferrocenium couple.

Time-resolved Microwave Conductivity (TRMC) was performed setting a film on a quartz substrate in a resonant cavity and probed by continuous microwaves at ~ 9.1 GHz. The third harmonic generation (THG; 355 nm) of a Nd:YAG laser (Continuum Inc., Surelite II, 5-8 ns pulse duration, 10 Hz) was used as an excitation source (incident photon density, $I_0 = 9.1 \times 10^{15}$ photons cm^{-2} pulse $^{-1}$). The photoconductivity transient $\Delta\sigma$ was converted to the product of the quantum yield (ϕ) and the sum of the charge carrier mobilities, $\Sigma\mu$ ($= \mu_h + \mu_e$) by $\phi\Sigma\mu = \Delta\sigma (eI_0F_{\text{light}})^{-1}$, where e and F_{light} are the unit charge of a single electron and the correction (or filling) factor, respectively.

OPTOELECTRONIC AND ELECTROCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION:

Figure S1. NICS of compounds 3a, 3b, 4 and 5.

Figure S2. CH_2Cl_2 solutions of **3b**, **4** and **5** exposed to visible light (left) and UV light (right).

Figure S3. Calculated absorption spectrum using TD-DFT at the B3LYP-CH₂Cl₂-6-311+g(2d,p)/B3LYP-6-31g(d,p) level of compounds **3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5**.

Figure S4. FP-TRMC ($\lambda_{\text{exc}}=355 \text{ nm}$) of a) **3a**, b) **3b**, c) **4** and d) **5**.

Table S1. Summary of photophysical data and energy levels of compounds 3a, 3b, 4 and 5.

entry	compound	$\lambda_{\max, \text{abs, exp}}$ (nm)	$\lambda_{\max, \text{abs, calc}}$ (nm) ^[a]	λ_{onset} (nm)	$\lambda_{\max, \text{ems, exp}}$ (nm)	$\lambda_{\max, \text{ems, calc}}$ (nm) ^[a]	Stokes' shift (cm ⁻¹)	Φ_f (%)
1	3a	456	501	471	470	515	6532	8.25 ± 0.20 ^[b]
2	3b	472	525	489	502	540	12661	8.81 ± 0.22 ^[b]
3	4	620	777	640	632	810	3062	36.47±0.59 ^[c]
4	5	659	795	681	670	827	2491	10.28±0.28 ^[c]

[a] Calculated using TD-DFT at the B3LYP-CH₂Cl₂-6-311+g(2d,p)/B3LYP-6-31g(d,p) level; [b] Calculated using 9,10-Diphenylanthracene (DPA) in cyclohexane as reference standard;¹ [c] Calculated using Oxacine 170 in EtOH as reference standard.²

Quantum yields $\Phi_{f,x}$ were calculated following the next equation:

$$\Phi_{f,x} = \Phi_{f,st} \cdot \frac{F_x \cdot f_{st}(\lambda_{ex,st}) \cdot \eta_x^2}{F_{st} \cdot f_x(\lambda_{ex,x}) \cdot \eta_{st}^2}$$

Where $\Phi_{f,st}$ stands for the quantum yield of the reference standard, F_x for the measured fluorescence (area) of a solution at known concentration of products **3a**, **3b**, **4** or **5** at the excitation wavelength, F_{st} for the measured fluorescence (area) of a solution at known concentration of the reference standard at the excitation wavelength, $f_x(\lambda_{ex}) = 1 - 10^{A_x(\lambda_{ex})}$ where $A_x(\lambda_{ex})$ stands for the absorbance of a solution at known concentration of products **3a**, **3b**, **4** or **5** at the excitation wavelength, $f_{st}(\lambda_{ex}) = 1 - 10^{A_{st}(\lambda_{ex})}$ where $A_{st}(\lambda_{ex})$ stands for the absorbance of a solution at known concentration of the reference standard at the excitation wavelength, η_x is the index of refraction of the solvent of the solutions of compounds **3a**, **3b**, **4** or **5** and η_{st} is the index of refraction of the solvent of the solution of the reference standard.

The error was calculated as follows:

$$Error = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (\Phi_{f,x_i} - \overline{\Phi_{f,x}})^2}}{n}$$

To measure quantum yield of **3a** 9,10-Diphenylanthracene (DPA) was selected as reference standard ($\Phi_{f,DPA} = 0.93$)¹ at $7.42 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ in cyclohexane ($\eta_{cy} = 1.45$). The excitation wavelength was set at 340 nm and 3 solutions at different concentrations of **3a** in CHCl₃ ($\eta_{CHCl_3} = 1.42$) were analyzed:

entry	Concentration ($\times 10^{-7} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)	$\Phi_{f,3a}$ (%)
1	5.87	8.68
2	4.40	8.22
3	2.94	7.85

The quantum yield of **3a** is expressed as the average of the three measurements and the error associated:

$$\overline{\Phi_{f,3a}} = 8.25 \pm 0.20$$

To measure quantum yield of **3b** 9,10-Diphenylanthracene (DPA) was selected as reference standard ($\Phi_{f,DPA} = 0.93$)¹ at $7.42 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ in cyclohexane ($\eta_{cy} = 1.45$). The excitation wavelength was set at 345 nm and 3 solutions at different concentrations of **3b** in CHCl_3 ($\eta_{\text{CHCl}_3} = 1.44$) were analyzed:

entry	Concentration ($\times 10^{-7} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)	$\Phi_{f,3b}$ (%)
1	7.97	8.29
2	5.47	9.22
3	3.63	8.92

The quantum yield of **3b** is expressed as the average of the three measurements and the error associated:

$$\overline{\Phi_{f,3b}} = 8.81 \pm 0.22$$

To measure quantum yield of **4** oxacine 170 was selected as reference standard ($\Phi_{f,oxacine\ 170} = 0.58$)² at $3.54 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ in EtOH ($\eta_{EtOH} = 1.37$). The excitation wavelength was set at 540 nm and 3 solutions at different concentrations of **4** in CHCl_3 ($\eta_{\text{CHCl}_3} = 1.44$) were analyzed:

entry	Concentration ($\times 10^{-6} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)	$\Phi_{f,4}$ (%)
1	0.32	36.76
2	0.81	35.89
3	1.62	34.82

The quantum yield of **4** is expressed as the average of the three measurements and the error associated:

$$\overline{\Phi_{f,4}} = 36.47 \pm 0.59$$

To measure quantum yield of **5** oxacine 170 was selected as reference standard ($\Phi_{f,oxacine\ 170} = 0.58$)² at $3.54 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ in EtOH ($\eta_{EtOH} = 1.37$). The excitation wavelength was set at 525 nm and 3 solutions at different concentrations of **5** in CHCl_3 ($\eta_{\text{CHCl}_3} = 1.44$) were analyzed:

entry	Concentration ($\times 10^{-6} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)	$\Phi_{f,5}$ (%)
1	1.60	10.69
2	2.13	10.55
3	3.20	9.61

The quantum yield of **4** is expressed as the average of the three measurements and the error associated:

$$\overline{\Phi_{f,5}} = 10.28 \pm 0.28$$

Table S2. First excitations TD-DFT at the B3LYP-CH₂Cl₂-6-311+g(2d,p)/B3LYP-6-31g(d,p) level of compounds 3a, 3b, 4 and 5.

entry	compound	energy (eV)	energy (nm)	osc. strength
1	3a	2.47	501	0.20
2	3b	2.36	525	0.13
3	4	1.59	777	0.17
4	5	1.56	795	0.18

All have a HOMO-LUMO transition contribution $\geq 90\%$.

Table S3. Half-wave, anodic and cathodic peak potentials of compounds 3a, 3b, 4 and 5.

entry	compound	$E_{1/2, \text{red1}}$ (eV)	$E_{1/2, \text{red2}}$ (eV)	$E_{1/2, \text{red3}}$ (eV)	$E_{\text{pc, red1}}$ (eV)	$E_{\text{ac, red1}}$ (eV)	$E_{\text{pc, red2}}$ (eV)	$E_{\text{ac, red2}}$ (eV)	$E_{\text{pc, red3}}$ (eV)	$E_{\text{ac, red3}}$ (eV)
1	3a	-1.52	-1.72	-	-1.54	-1.50	-1.76	-1.67	-	-
2	3b	-1.54	-1.71	-	-1.60	1.47	-1.76	-1.65	-	-
3	4	-0.93	-1.04	-	-0.97	-0.92	-1.08	-1.00	-	-
4	5	-0.69	-0.81	-1.23	-0.70	-0.67	-0.84	-0.77	-1.40	-1.11

CV in 0.1 M solution of *n*Bu₄NPF₆ in CH₂Cl₂. Potentials versus Fc/Fc⁺.

Table S4. Experimental energy levels of compounds 3a, 3b, 4 and 5.

entry	compound	$E_{\text{gap(opt)}}^{\text{[a]}}$ (eV)	$E_{\text{(LUMO)}}^{\text{[b]}}$ (eV)	$E_{\text{(HOMO)}}^{\text{[c]}}$ (eV)
1	3a	2.63	-3.59	-6.22
2	3b	2.49	-3.60	-6.09
3	4	1.94	-3.92	-5.86
4	5	1.82	-4.17	-5.99

[a] $E_{\text{gap(opt)}}$ calculated from λ_{onset} measured in chloroform; [b] $E_{\text{(LUMO)}} = -e(4.8 \text{ V} + E_{\text{Red}})$; [c] $E_{\text{(HOMO)}} = E_{\text{(LUMO)}} - E_{\text{gap(opt)}}$.

Table S5. Orbitals eigenvalues at the B3LYP-CH₂Cl₂-6-311+g(2d,p)/B3LYP-6-31g(d,p) level of theory of compounds 3a, 3b, 4 and 5. All energies in eV.

entry	compound	LUMO+2	LUMO+1	LUMO	HOMO	HOMO-1	HOMO-2	gap
1	3a	-1.95	-2.74	-3.05	-5.96	-6.09	-6.21	2.91
2	3b	-1.89	-2.71	-3.03	-5.86	-6.08	-6.12	2.83
3	4	-2.16	-3.60	-3.84	-5.77	-5.91	-6.16	1.93
4	5	-2.23	-3.55	-3.78	-5.66	-5.77	-6.09	1.88

SYNTHETIC PROCEDURES:

For the preparation of *o*-phenylenediamine **11**,³ *o*-diamine-benzothiadiazole **12**,⁴ and *o*-diamine-phenazine **13**⁵ literature protocols were followed.

1,4-dibromo-2,5-diiodobenzene 7. A solution of 1,4-dibromobenzene **6** (15 g, 63.6 mmol) and iodine (62 g, 244 mmol, 3.8 equiv) in 120 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid was stirred at 130 °C for 16 h. The mixture was poured into ice-water and the precipitate was filtered and washed successively with 10% aqueous sodium bisulfite, H₂O and sodium bicarbonate. The mixture was later dissolved up in CHCl₃ (60 mL) and washed with 10% aqueous sodium bisulfite (2x30 mL), sodium bicarbonate (2x30 mL), and H₂O (1x30 mL). After the removal of the solvent a white solid (14 g, 80%) was obtained. The spectroscopic data recorded for this material (vide infra) were in good agreement with those reported in the literature.⁶ ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ: 8.05 (s, 2H). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (CDCl₃, 125 MHz) δ: 142.5, 129.4, 101.5.

(2,5-dibromo-1,4-phenylene)bis(ethyne-2,1-diyl)bis(trimethylsilane) 8. To a mixture of **7** (10 g, 20.5 mmol), PPh₃ (538 mg, 2.05 mmol, 10 mol %), CuI (781 mg, 4.1 mmol, 20 mol %) and PdCl₂(PPh₃)₂ (720 mg, 1.03 mmol, 5 mol %) were added degassed THF (120 mL) and ⁴Pr₂NH (40 mL) via cannula at 0 °C. Trimethylsilylacetylene (6.25 mL, 45.1 mmol, 2.2 equiv) was dropwise added at this temperature and then, the reaction was allowed to warm up to room temperature. After 16 h, the crude reaction was diluted in AcOEt (150 mL) and poured into an ice-HCl bath (50g and 150 mL, 2 M). The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted (2x75 mL, AcOEt). The combined organic layers were then dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and filtered. After the removal of the solvent a yellowish solid was obtained and after several washings with MeOH the desired product was isolated as a white solid (5.6 g, 13.1 mmol, 64%). The spectroscopic data recorded for this material (vide infra) were in good agreement with those reported in the literature.⁷ ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ: 7.67 (s, 2H), 0.27 (s, 18H). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (CDCl₃, 125 MHz) δ: 136.5, 126.6, 123.9, 103.2, 101.5, -0.15.

2',5'-bis((trimethylsilyl)ethynyl)-1,1':4,1''-terphenyl 9a. To a solution of **8** (2.80 g, 6.54 mmol) and phenylboronic acid (1.83 g, 15 mmol, 2.3 equiv) in toluene:water (5:1, 66 mL), K₂CO₃ (4.5 g, 32.7 mmol, 5 equiv) and Pd(PPh₃)₄ (1.13 g, 0.98 mmol, 15 mol %) were added. After, the mixture was heated to reflux and reacted overnight. The solvent was removed and the yellowish solid was thoroughly washed with MeOH. Then it was dissolved up in hexane:DCM (1:1) and after the removal of the solvent, the solid was washed with MeOH. The titled compound was isolated as a white solid (1.66 g, 3.92 mmol, 60%). The spectroscopic data recorded for this material (vide infra) were in good agreement with those reported in the literature.⁸ ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ: 7.75-7.65 (m, 6H), 7.51-7.36 (m, 6H), 0.19 (s, 18H). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (CDCl₃, 125 MHz) δ: 142.8, 139.2, 134.3, 129.4, 128.0, 127.8, 127.6, 121.9, 104.4, 99.6, -0.21.

2',5'-diethynyl-1,1':4,1''-terphenyl 10a. To a solution of **9a** (1.66 g, 3.92 mmol) in hexane (40 mL), THF (20 mL), MeOH (80 mL) and saturated K₂CO₃ (aq, 8 mL) was added. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 4 h and after the removal of the solvent the white solid was washed with H₂O and MeOH. The titled product was isolated as a white solid (1.09 g, 3.92 mmol, quantitative) The spectroscopic data recorded for this material (vide infra) were in good agreement with those reported in the literature.⁸ ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ: 7.71-7.57 (m, 6H), 7.50-7.37 (m, 6H), 3.14 (s, 2H). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (CDCl₃, 125 MHz) δ: 142.9, 138.9, 134.9, 129.1, 128.1, 127.9, 121.1, 82.5, 81.8.

Dibenzo[a,h]anthracene 1a. After drying PtCl_2 (261 mg, 0.98 mmol, 25 mol %) under vacuum for 1 h a solution of **10a** (1.09 g, 3.9 mmol) in toluene (50 mL) was added via cannula at room temperature. The mixture was stirred at 110 °C for 2 h and filtered through a short plug of Celite® using CH_2Cl_2 as eluant. The solvent was removed and the brown solid was successively washed with MeOH, EtOH and *i*PrOH until no coloration was observed in the washings. The titled product was isolated as a light brown solid (621 mg, 2.22 mmol, 57%). The spectroscopic data recorded for this material (vide infra) were in good agreement with those reported in the literature.⁸ ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ : 9.15 (s, 2H), 8.79 (d, 2H, $J = 8.1$ Hz), 7.96 (d, 2H, $J = 9.0$ Hz), 7.92 (dd, 2H, $J = 7.7, 1.5$ Hz), 7.79-7.62 (m, 6H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (CDCl_3 , 125 MHz) δ : 132.2, 131.0, 130.5, 129.3, 128.8, 127.6, 127.4, 127.2, 127.0, 123.1, 122.3.

Dibenzo[a,h]anthracene-5,6,12,13-tetraone 2a. To a solution of **1a** (621 mg, 2.22 mmol) and $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (116 mg, 0.56 mmol, 25 mol %) in $\text{CHCl}_3:\text{CH}_3\text{CN}:\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1:1:1.2, 32 mL) NaIO_4 (4.27 g, 20.0 mmol, 9 equiv) was added portionwise. The mixture was stirred at 60 °C for 18 h and filtered by suction. Then, the reddish solid was suspended in AcOH (6 mL), $\text{Na}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (132 mg, 0.5 mmol, 23 mol %) was added and the mixture was stirred at 120 °C for 30 min. The crude was filtered and thoroughly washed with MeOH, CHCl_3 , Acetone and Et_2O to yield a dark red product (112 mg, 0.33 mmol, 14%). ATR-IR (cm^{-1}): 1672 (C=O st). Due to the insolubility of the product it was used in the next reaction step without further characterization.

Compound 3a. To a solution of **2a** (5.3 mg, 0.015 mmol) in $\text{CHCl}_3:\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$ (3:1, 5.0 mL) diamine **11** (17.5 mg, 0.037 mmol, 2.5 equiv) was added as a CHCl_3 solution (500 μL). Then, anhydrous Na_2SO_4 (15 mg) was added and the mixture was stirred at 90 °C for 48 h. After cooling to room temperature saturated NaHCO_3 (aq, 5 mL) was slowly added and the organic layer was separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with CHCl_3 (3 x 5 mL) and after the removal of the solvent the solid was filtered by suction and washed with MeOH. After flash chromatography (Petroleum ether: CHCl_3 (1:1), Rf: 0.50), the titled product was isolated as a yellow solid (11 mg, 0.0089 mmol, 59%). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ : 10.68 (s, 2H), 9.59 (dd, 2H, $J = 8.0, 1.4$ Hz), 8.97 (d, 2H, $J = 8.0$ Hz), 8.06-8.00 (m, 4H), 7.88-7.81 (m, 2H), 7.79-7.76 (m, 2H), 1.38-1.33 (m, 42H), 1.33-1.30 (m, 42H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (CDCl_3 , 125 MHz) δ : 143.5, 142.9, 142.8, 142.1, 135.1, 134.0, 132.6, 131.82, 130.77, 130.67, 128.4, 127.3, 124.4, 124.2, 124.0, 121.8, 104.6, 103.8, 100.2, 100.0, 19.1, 19.0, 11.8, 11.7. UV-vis (nm): 283, 290, 331, 345, 416, 440, 456. HRMS (MALDI-TOF) (m/z): calculated for $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, $\text{C}_{78}\text{H}_{99}\text{N}_4\text{Si}_4$: 1203.6943; found: 1203.6923.

(4,4''-di-tert-butyl-[1,1':4',1''-terphenyl]-2',5'-diyl)bis(ethyne-2,1-diyl)bis(trimethylsilane) 9b. To a solution of **8** (2.8 g, 6.54 mmol) and 4-*tert*-butylphenylboronic acid (2.7 g, 15 mmol, 2.3 equiv) in toluene:water (5:1, 66 mL), K_2CO_3 (4.5 g, 32.7 mmol, 5 equiv) and $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (1.13 g, 0.98 mmol, 15 mol %) were added. The solvent was removed and the yellowish solid was thoroughly washed with MeOH. Then it was dissolved up in hexane:DCM (1:1) and after the removal of the solvent, the solid was washed with MeOH. The titled compound was isolated as a white solid (2.7 g, 5.05 mmol, 77%). The spectroscopic data recorded for this material (vide infra) were in good agreement with those reported in the literature.⁹ ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ : 7.71-7.56 (m, 6H), 7.51-7.40 (m, 4H), 1.39 (s, 18H), 0.15 (s, 18H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (CDCl_3 , 125 MHz) δ : 151.0, 142.9, 136.7, 134.4, 129.3, 125.2, 122.1, 105.9, 99.7, 35.1, 31.8, -0.11.

4,4''-di-tert-butyl-2',5'-diethynyl-1,1':4',1''-terphenyl 10b. To a solution of **9b** (2.33 g, 4.35 mmol) in hexane (45 mL), THF (23 mL), MeOH (90 mL) and saturated K_2CO_3 (aq, 9 mL) was added. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 4 h and after the removal of the solvent the white solid was washed with H_2O and MeOH. The titled product was isolated as a white solid (1.74 g, 4.35 mmol, quantitative). The spectroscopic data recorded for this material (vide infra) were in good agreement with those reported in the literature.⁹ ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400

MHz) δ : 7.64 (s, 2H), 7.58 (d, 4H, $J = 8.4$ Hz), 7.46 (d, 4H, $J = 8.4$ Hz), 3.14 (s, 2H), 1.38 (s, 18H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (CDCl_3 , 125 MHz) δ : 151.0, 142.5, 146.1, 135.2, 128.9, 125.2, 125.1, 83.0, 81.8, 34.8, 31.5.

3,10-di-tert-butylidibenzo[a,h]anthracene 1b. After drying PtCl_2 (247 mg, 0.93 mmol, 25 mol %) under vacuum for 1 h a solution of **1b** (1.45 mg, 3.71 mmol) in toluene (50 mL) was added via cannula at room temperature. The mixture was stirred at 110 °C for 2 h and filtered through a short plug of celite® using CH_2Cl_2 as eluant. The solvent was removed and the brown solid was successively washed with MeOH, EtOH and i PrOH until no coloration was observed in the washings. The titled product was isolated as a light brown solid (906 mg, 2.31 mmol, 63%). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ : 9.11 (s, 2H), 8.79 (d, 2H, $J = 8.6$ Hz), 7.95 (d, 2H, $J = 8.9$ Hz), 7.87 (d, 2H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 7.78 (dd, 2H, $J = 8.6, 2.1$ Hz), 7.74 (d, 2H, $J = 8.9$ Hz), 1.49 (s, 18H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (CDCl_3 , 125 MHz) δ : 150.0, 131.9, 130.8, 129.0, 128.2, 127.6, 127.5, 125.1, 124.7, 122.8, 122.0, 35.0, 31.6. HRMS (MALDI-TOF) (m/z): calculated for $[\text{M}]^+$, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{30}$: 390,2348; found: 390,2348.

3,10-di-tert-butylidibenzo[a,h]anthracene-5,6,12,13-tetraone 2b. To a solution of **1b** (906 mg, 2.3 mmol) and $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (119 mg, 0.57 mmol, 25 mol %) in $\text{CHCl}_3:\text{CH}_3\text{CN}:\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1:1:1.2, 32 mL) NaIO_4 (4.3g, 20.2 mmol, 8.8 equiv) was added portionwise. The mixture was stirred at 60 °C for 18 h and filtered by suction. Then, the reddish solid was suspended in AcOH (6 mL), $\text{Na}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (132 mg, 0.5 mmol, 22 mol %) was added and the mixture was stirred at 120 °C for 30 min. The crude was filtrated through a plug of SiO_2 using CHCl_3 as eluant. After evaporation of the solvents the solid was purified through flash chromatography (CHCl_3 , Rf: 0.45). The titled product was isolated as a dark red solid (170 mg, 0.38 mmol, 17%). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ : 8.74 (s, 2H), 8.25 (d, 2H, $J = 2.2$ Hz), 8.10 (d, 2H, $J = 8.4$ Hz), 7.84 (dd, 2H, $J = 8.4, 2.2$ Hz), 1.40 (s, 18H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (CDCl_3 , 125 MHz) δ : 180.4, 179.5, 154.6, 136.1, 134.8, 134.1, 131.9, 131.0, 127.8, 126.1, 124.9, 35.3, 31.1. ATR-FTIR (cm^{-1}): 2968 (C-H st), 1678 (C=O st). HRMS (ESI-TOF) (m/z): calculated for $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_4$: 451.1904; found: 451.1902.

Compound 3b. To a solution of **2b** (6.7 mg, 0.015 mmol) in $\text{CHCl}_3:\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$ (3:1, 5.0 mL) diamine **11** (17.5 mg, 0.037 mmol, 2.5 equiv) was added as a CHCl_3 solution (500 μL). Then, anhydrous Na_2SO_4 (15 mg) was added and the mixture was stirred at 90 °C for 48 h. After cooling to room temperature saturated NaHCO_3 (aq, 5 mL) was slowly added and the organic layer was separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with CHCl_3 (3 x 5 mL) and after the removal of the solvent the solid was filtered by suction and washed with MeOH. After flash chromatography (Petroleum ether: CHCl_3 (1:1), Rf: 0.60), the titled product was isolated as a yellow solid (15.1 mg, 0.011 mmol, 76%). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ : 10.62 (s, 2H), 9.56 (d, 2H, $J = 2.1$ Hz), 8.90 (d, 2H, $J = 8.7$ Hz), 8.03 (s, 4H), 7.90 (dd, 2H, $J = 8.5, 2.2$ Hz), 1.58 (s, 18H), 1.39-1.34 (m, 42H), 1.30-1.22 (m, 42H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (CDCl_3 , 125 MHz) δ : 151.7, 144.0, 143.2, 142.2, 142, 135.2, 134.7, 131.6, 131.5, 130.4, 130.2, 128.3, 124.4, 124.3, 123.9, 123.4, 121.5, 104.6, 104.5, 100.1, 100.0, 35.3, 31.6. UV-vis (nm): 283, 292, 350, 337, 416, 438, 472. HRMS (MALDI-TOF) (m/z): calculated for $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, $\text{C}_{86}\text{H}_{115}\text{N}_4\text{Si}_4$: 1315.8195; found: 1315.8206.

Compound 4. To a solution of **2b** (50 mg, 0.11 mmol) in $\text{CHCl}_3:\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$ (3:1, 15 mL) diamine **12** (146.2 mg, 0.277 mmol, 2.5 equiv) was added as a CHCl_3 solution (1.5 mL). Then, anhydrous Na_2SO_4 (225 mg) was added and the mixture was stirred at 90 °C for 48 h. After cooling to room temperature saturated NaHCO_3 (aq, 15 mL) was slowly added and the organic layer was separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with CHCl_3 (3 x 15 mL) and after the removal of the solvent the solid was purified through flash chromatography (Petroleum ether: CHCl_3 (1:1), Rf: 0.50). The titled product was isolated as a red solid (37 mg, 0.024 mmol, 22%). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ : 10.49 (s, 2H), 9.53 (d, 2H, J = 2.2 Hz), 8.81 (d, 2H, J = 8.5 Hz), 7.92 (dd, 2H, J = 8.5, 2.2 Hz), 1.59 (s,

18H), 1.47-1.39 (m, 42H), 1.38-1.28 (m, 42H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (CDCl_3 , 125 MHz) δ : 155.7, 155.4, 152.4, 146.1, 145.4, 141.70, 141.65, 132.5, 132.3, 130.9, 130.1, 129.4, 124.2, 124.1, 122.5, 114.6, 114.5, 110.5, 110.4, 102.3, 102.0, 35.3, 31.6, 19.21, 19.16, 12.0, 11.8. UV-vis (nm): 285, 292, 305, 321, 355, 368, 451, 477, 496, 527, 573, 620. HRMS (MALDI-TOF) (m/z): calculated for $[\text{M}+\text{Ag}]^+$, $\text{C}_{86}\text{H}_{110}\text{N}_8\text{S}_2\text{Si}_4\text{Ag}$: 1537,6423; found: 1537.6513.

Compound 5. To a solution of **2b** (20 mg, 0.044 mmol) in $\text{CHCl}_3:\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$ (3:1, 6 mL) diamine **13** (62.8 mg, 0.093 mmol, 2.1 equiv) was added as a CHCl_3 solution (2 mL). Then, anhydrous Na_2SO_4 (150 mg) was added and the mixture was stirred at 90 °C for 48 h. After cooling to room temperature saturated NaHCO_3 (aq, 6 mL) was slowly added and the organic layer was separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with CHCl_3 (3 x 15 mL) and after the removal of the solvent the solid was purified through flash chromatography (Petroleum ether: AcOEt (98:2), Rf: 0.75). The titled product was isolated as a purple solid (25 mg, 0.017 mmol, 37%). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ : 10.65 (s, 2H), 9.67

(d, 2H, J = 2.2 Hz), 8.92 (d, 2H, J = 8.6 Hz), 8.41-8.30 (m, 4H), 8.01 (dd, 2H, J = 8.6, 2.2 Hz), 7.98-7.87 (m, 4H), 1.66 (s, 18H), 1.58-1.53 (m, 42H), 1.50-1.44 (m, 42H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (CDCl_3 , 125 MHz) δ : 152.1, 146.1, 145.3, 145.01, 144.96, 143.6, 143.4, 141.9, 141.8, 132.3, 131.74, 131.71, 130.8, 130.33, 130.30, 130.1, 129.3, 124.2, 124.0, 122.54, 122.52, 122.5, 111.2, 111.1, 103.1, 102.9, 35.2, 31.5, 19.20, 19.16, 12.0, 11.8. UV-vis (nm): 283, 297, 309, 330, 361, 377, 445, 477, 505, 528, 608, 659. HRMS (MALDI-TOF) (m/z): calculated for $[\text{M}+\text{Ag}]^+$, $\text{C}_{98}\text{H}_{118}\text{N}_8\text{Si}_4\text{Ag}$: 1625,7606; found: 1625,7564.

^1H and ^{13}C NMR Spectra:

Figure S5. ^1H -NMR of product 7 in CDCl_3 (400 MHz).

Figure S6. ^{13}C -NMR of product 7 in CDCl_3 (125 MHz).

Figure S7. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of product **8** in CDCl_3 (400 MHz).

Figure S8. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of product **8** in CDCl_3 (125 MHz).

Figure S9. ¹H-NMR of product **9a** in CDCl₃ (400 MHz).

Figure S10. ¹³C-NMR of product **9a** in CDCl₃ (125 MHz).

Figure S11. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of product **10a** in CDCl_3 (400 MHz).

Figure S12. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of product **10a** in CDCl_3 (125 MHz).

Figure S13. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of product **1a** in CDCl_3 (400 MHz).

Figure S14. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of product **1a** in CDCl_3 (125 MHz).

Figure S15. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of product **3a** in CDCl_3 (400 MHz).

Figure S16. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of product **3a** in CDCl_3 (125 MHz).

Figure S17. ¹³C-NMR of product **9b** in CDCl₃ (400 MHz).

Figure S18. ¹³C-NMR of product **9b** in CDCl₃ (125 MHz).

10b, Ar = *p*-^tBuC₆H₄

Figure S19. ¹³C-NMR of product **10b** in CDCl₃ (400 MHz).

Figure S20. ¹³C-NMR of product **10b** in CDCl₃ (125 MHz).

Figure S21. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of product **1b** in CDCl_3 (400 MHz).

Figure S22. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of product **1b** in CDCl_3 (125 MHz).

Figure S23. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of product **2b** in CDCl_3 (400 MHz).

Figure S24. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of product **2b** in CDCl_3 (125 MHz).

Figure S25. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of product **3b** in CDCl_3 (400 MHz).

Figure S26. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of product **3b** in CDCl_3 (125 MHz).

Figure S27. ¹H-NMR of product 4 in CDCl₃ (400 MHz).

Figure S28. ¹³C-NMR of product 4 in CDCl₃ (125 MHz).

Figure S29. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of product **5** in CDCl_3 (400 MHz).

Figure S30. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of product **5** in CDCl_3 (125 MHz).

IR SPECTRA

Figure S31. IR spectra of compounds **2a** and **2b**.

X-RAY CRYSTALLOGRAPHY DATA:

Product **3a**:

Compound **3a** (3 mg) was dissolved up in CH₂Cl₂ and recrystallized by liquid-liquid diffusion from MeOH. Needle shaped crystals were obtained after three days. Afterwards, a suitable crystal was selected and placed on an Agilent SuperNova, single source at offset, Atlas diffractometer. The crystal was kept at 150.01(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2¹⁰, the structure was solved with the ShelXS¹¹ structure solution program using Direct Methods and refined with the ShelXL¹² refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

Crystal structure determination of **3a**.

Crystal Data for **3a**: triclinic, space group P-1 (no. 2), a = 14.4215(12) Å, b = 14.4364(10) Å, c = 17.8777(16) Å, α = 83.360(6)°, β = 73.748(7)°, γ = 77.318(6)°, V = 3480.3(5) Å³, Z = 2, T = 150.01(10) K, μ (CuK α) = 1.125 mm⁻¹, D_{calc} = 1.149 g/cm³, 25753 reflections measured (7.168° ≤ 2 Θ ≤ 138°), 12930 unique (R_{int} = 0.0901, R_{sigma} = 0.1491) which were used in all calculations. The final R₁ was 0.0731 (I > 2 σ (I)) and wR₂ was 0.1804 (all data).

Figure S32. Thermal ellipsoid plot for compound **3a** at 50% ellipsoid contour probability.

Table S6. Crystal data and structure refinement for compound 3a.

Identification code	a20190007_JIM18134T150K
Empirical formula	C ₇₈ H ₉₈ N ₄ Si ₄
Formula weight	1203.96
Temperature/K	150.01(10)
Crystal system	triclinic
Space group	P-1
a/Å	14.4215(12)
b/Å	14.4364(10)
c/Å	17.8777(16)
α /°	83.360(6)
β /°	73.748(7)
γ /°	77.318(6)
Volume/Å ³	3480.3(5)
Z	2
$\rho_{\text{calc}}/\text{cm}^3$	1.149
μ/mm^{-1}	1.125
F(000)	1300.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.89 × 0.092 × 0.048
Radiation	CuK α (λ = 1.54184)
2 Θ range for data collection/°	7.168 to 138
Index ranges	-17 ≤ h ≤ 17, -17 ≤ k ≤ 14, -21 ≤ l ≤ 21
Reflections collected	25753
Independent reflections	12930 [R _{int} = 0.0901, R _{sigma} = 0.1491]
Data/restraints/parameters	12930/0/799
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	0.965
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2 σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.0731, wR ₂ = 0.1445
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.1376, wR ₂ = 0.1804
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.48/-0.41

Product 3b:

Compound **3b** (5 mg) was dissolved up in CH₂Cl₂ and recrystallized by liquid-liquid diffusion from MeOH. Needle shaped crystals were obtained after three days. Afterwards, a suitable crystal was selected and placed on an Agilent SuperNova, single source at offset, Atlas diffractometer. The crystal was kept at 150.01(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2¹⁰, the structure was solved with the ShelXS¹¹ structure solution program using Direct Methods and refined with the ShelXL¹² refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

Crystal structure determination of 3b.

Crystal Data for **3b**: monoclinic, space group P2₁ (no. 4), $a = 14.6051(18)$ Å, $b = 14.6023(12)$ Å, $c = 20.160(3)$ Å, $\beta = 97.200(13)^\circ$, $V = 4265.5(9)$ Å³, $Z = 2$, $T = 150.00(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{CuK}\alpha) = 0.967$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.025$ g/cm³, 34131 reflections measured ($7.07^\circ \leq 2\Theta \leq 138^\circ$), 12699 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.1174$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.1352$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.0788 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.2146 (all data).

Figure S33. Thermal ellipsoid plot for compound **3b** at 50% ellipsoid contour probability.

Table S7. Crystal data and structure refinement for compound 3b.

Identification code	a20190004_JIM180133T150K2
Empirical formula	C ₈₆ H ₁₁₄ N ₄ Si ₄
Formula weight	1316.17
Temperature/K	150.00(10)
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	P2 ₁
a/Å	14.6051(18)
b/Å	14.6023(12)
c/Å	20.160(3)
α/°	90.0
β/°	97.200(13)
γ/°	90.0
Volume/Å ³	4265.5(9)
Z	2
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.025
μ/mm ⁻¹	0.967
F(000)	1428.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.583 × 0.314 × 0.118
Radiation	CuKα (λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	7.07 to 138
Index ranges	-17 ≤ h ≤ 17, -17 ≤ k ≤ 11, -24 ≤ l ≤ 24
Reflections collected	34131
Independent reflections	12699 [R _{int} = 0.1174, R _{sigma} = 0.1352]
Data/restraints/parameters	12699/103/878
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	0.971
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.0788, wR ₂ = 0.1785
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.1288, wR ₂ = 0.2146
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.66/-0.34

Product 4:

Compound **4** (9 mg) was dissolved up in CH₂Cl₂ and recrystallized by liquid-liquid diffusion from MeOH. Needle shaped crystals were obtained after three days. Afterwards, a suitable crystal was selected and placed on an Agilent SuperNova, single source at offset, Atlas diffractometer. The crystal was kept at 150.01(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2¹⁰, the structure was solved with the ShelXS¹¹ structure solution program using Direct Methods and refined with the ShelXL¹² refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

Crystal structure determination of **4**.

Crystal Data for **4**: triclinic, space group P-1 (no. 2), a = 17.4140(9) Å, b = 20.0991(17) Å, c = 20.8980(18) Å, α = 99.233(7)°, β = 12.874(6)°, γ = 107.208(6)°, V = 6114.2(9) Å³, Z = 2, T = 150.01(10) K, μ (CuK α) = 1.521 mm⁻¹, D_{calc} = 1.167 g/cm³, 45541 reflections measured (6.91° ≤ 2 θ ≤ 137.984°), 22694 unique (R_{int} = 0.1893, R_{sigma} = 0.2690) which were used in all calculations. The final R₁ was 0.1317 (I > 2 σ (I)) and wR₂ was 0.4600 (all data).

Figure S34. Thermal ellipsoid plot for compound **4** at 50% ellipsoid contour probability.

Table S8. Crystal data and structure refinement for compound 4.

Identification code	a20180082_JIM18014
Empirical formula	C ₁₂₉ H ₁₆₅ N ₁₂ S ₃ Si ₆
Formula weight	2148.44
Temperature/K	150.01(10)
Crystal system	triclinic
Space group	P-1
a/Å	17.4140(9)
b/Å	20.0991(17)
c/Å	20.8980(18)
α/°	99.233(7)
β/°	112.874(6)
γ/°	107.208(6)
Volume/Å ³	6114.2(9)
Z	2
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.167
μ/mm ⁻¹	1.521
F(000)	2310.0
Radiation	CuKα (λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	6.91 to 137.984
Index ranges	-21 ≤ h ≤ 18, -24 ≤ k ≤ 24, -25 ≤ l ≤ 24
Reflections collected	45541
Independent reflections	22694 [R _{int} = 0.1893, R _{sigma} = 0.2690]
Data/restraints/parameters	22694/380/1468
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	0.955
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.1317, wR ₂ = 0.3183
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.3079, wR ₂ = 0.4600
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.73/-0.92

Alert level A:

PLAT026_ALERT_3_A Ratio Observed / Unique Reflections (too) Low. 25% Check

PLAT084_ALERT_3_A High wR2 Value (i.e. > 0.25). 0.46 Report

The crystals have good but very weak reflections. Several measurements are made but always the intensity that is obtained is very low, although a lot of exposure time is used. Due to this low intensity of diffraction there is a low relation between the observed and unique reflections.

There is a large disorder in the methyl groups in parts of the molecule along the structure. Restrictions of distance and angles, as well as restrictions in the ellipsoids are used to model the disorders. The low quality of the data obtained in the measurements and all this does not allow to reach better accorded factors.

Product **5**:

Compound **5** (7 mg) was dissolved up in CH₂Cl₂ and recrystallized by liquid-liquid diffusion from MeOH. Needle shaped crystals were obtained after three days. Afterwards, a suitable crystal was selected and placed on an Agilent SuperNova, single source at offset, Atlas diffractometer. The crystal was kept at 150.01(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2¹⁰, the structure was solved with the ShelXS¹¹ structure solution program using Direct Methods and refined with the ShelXL¹² refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

Crystal structure determination of **5**.

Crystal Data for **5**: triclinic, space group P-1 (no. 2), $a = 9.1952(7)$ Å, $b = 15.3983(10)$ Å, $c = 16.9447(12)$ Å, $\alpha = 103.841(6)^\circ$, $\beta = 90.728(6)^\circ$, $\gamma = 99.739(6)^\circ$, $V = 2292.4(3)$ Å³, $Z = 1$, $T = 150.01(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{CuK}\alpha) = 0.966$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.101$ g/cm³, 23843 reflections measured ($7.016^\circ \leq 2\Theta \leq 137.996^\circ$), 7154 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0745$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0863$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.1174 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.3869 (all data).

Figure S35. Thermal ellipsoid plot for compound **5** at 50% ellipsoid contour probability.

Table S9. Crystal data and structure refinement for compound 5.

Identification code	a20180092_jim18025suc
Empirical formula	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₈ Si ₄
Formula weight	1520.36
Temperature/K	150.01(10)
Crystal system	triclinic
Space group	P-1
a/Å	9.1952(7)
b/Å	15.3983(10)
c/Å	16.9447(12)
α/°	103.841(6)
β/°	90.728(6)
γ/°	99.739(6)
Volume/Å ³	2292.4(3)
Z	1
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.101
μ/mm ⁻¹	0.966
F(000)	818.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.717 × 0.077 × 0.041
Radiation	CuKα (λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	7.016 to 137.996
Index ranges	-8 ≤ h ≤ 10, -18 ≤ k ≤ 17, -19 ≤ l ≤ 20
Reflections collected	23843
Independent reflections	7154 [R _{int} = 0.0745, R _{sigma} = 0.0863]
Data/restraints/parameters	7154/160/649
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.194
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.1174, wR ₂ = 0.3287

Alert level A:

PLAT029_ALERT_3_A_diffn_measured_fraction_theta_full value Low 0.843

The crystals have low crystallinity and diffract very weakly. The crystals are needles very difficult to separate. It is not achieved after several crystallizations better quality crystals. The low symmetry and low crystallinity does not allow to achieve measurements with completeness greater than 85%. Several measurement are tried with a lot of exposure time and these are the best data that are obtained.

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